

**Ocean Cryosphere Exchanges in Antarctica:
Impacts on Climate and the Earth system**

OCEAN:ICE Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Policy (EDI)

Deliverable D9.9

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<https://ocean-ice.eu/>

About this document

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History of changes

Version	Date	Description	Authors (A) & Reviewers (R)
1	30 April 2023	First version delivered to the European Commission.	As listed on the second page.
2	3 October 2024	Revision after the 1st EC review, comments of the reviewers have been addressed: 1) Addition of a short Impact section. 2) Addition of a short description of when or how the policy will be updated. Delivery to the European Commission.	A: Andrea Herbert and Renuka Badhe (WiPS) R: Elaina Ford (BAS), Chiara Bearzotti (DMI)

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Publishable Summary

OCEAN:ICE aims to create a collaborative atmosphere that welcomes diversity of thought and allows everyone to thrive, no matter their background or characteristics and uphold excellence in the science that we do together. The present document presents the OCEAN:ICE Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion Policy. The policy is published on the project website and it a living document.

OCEAN:ICE Equity, Diversity and Inclusivity Mission Statement and policy

OCEAN:ICE aims to create a collaborative atmosphere that welcomes diversity of thought and allows everyone to thrive, no matter their background or characteristics and uphold excellence in the science that we do together.

As a large European project spanning 17 partner organisations in 10 countries, we, the OCEAN:ICE Project Members acknowledge that individual countries and partners may have differing regulations on Equity, Diversity and Inclusivity (EDI), and as the main employers of our researchers, we need to be contingent on these policies. We will apply our EDI policy for all project activities as individual organisational conditions permit. Where organisational practices are more developed and extensive, we aim to meet these.

We believe our science gains from an intersectional and inclusive approach, where people are encouraged to listen to and learn from those with different life experiences. Such differences may be visible or invisible, and include amongst many others gender, gender expression and identity, age, career stage and experience, race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, disability, medical conditions, religion and belief, economic status, work patterns, family situation, marriage and civil partnership, pregnancy and maternity, nationality and national origin, socio-economic background, communication style and approaches to how one thinks and works – and the many varied intersections of these.

In our activities, all of us in OCEAN:ICE aim to ensure the promotion of EDI principles, and to promote equal opportunities in the implementation of the project. We are already undertaking several actions to implement the spirit of EDI within OCEAN:ICE, for e.g. by even gender representation across the scientific leadership, training for early career researchers (ECR), and having ECR representatives in the Scientific Steering Committee, amongst other examples. We endeavour to further our EDI activities through this EDI policy:

Project meetings, work

1) Any OCEAN:ICE meetings will be within working hours (disparate time zones permitting); that the GA, and any other longer project or WP meetings are held during work days, in an accessible location. Hybrid, teleconferencing options will be provided for ensuring inclusivity for those unable to travel, and meeting recordings or meeting notes will be made available to those unable to join in.

2) OCEAN:ICE will uphold the right to reasonable accommodation for disability that extends to all work-related activities.

3) Working on weekends, public holidays and personal vacation will not be expected by the project team members, and flexible working will be supported.

4) Both Scientific Steering Committee, and individual WP leads will encourage a wide and active participation of a diverse team, and all contributions to publications, Deliverables and other products will be acknowledged.

5) The project participants [OCEAN:ICE Members] will use neutral language in all verbal and written communications and eliminate reference to specifications (e.g. gender, sexuality, disability, or other characteristics) to describe people.

Recruitment, training and project roles

6) Guidelines for recruitment are expected to ensure inclusive language in the advertisement for the position, to attract a diverse pool of applicants.

7) When new staff are hired for work on OCEAN:ICE, a part of their induction will include information about / awareness of this EDI policy

8) WP leads, Steering Committee, or any OCEAN:ICE individual will consider diversity in particular when assigning leadership and coordination roles for specific tasks within OCEAN:ICE.

9) Training of individuals, particularly ECRs, will be a priority.

Representing the project

10) When representing the project in talks, on conference panels the project participants will use inclusive language, and will aim to participate in panels that include [at least one person of another gender/various career stages/ not including Chair or moderator].

11) When we are the organisers of events, panel discussions and or conference sessions, we will take utmost care to ensure a diverse group of individuals, including those at early career stages, are involved in both the organisation and speaking.

Implementation

Responsibilities for general implementation

All WP Leads, Task Leads and participants are responsible for ensuring that this EDI Policy is implemented in their WPs, task teams and as individuals acting on behalf of OCEAN:ICE.

Resolution of feedback or complaints received

The project will make an anonymous form (<https://forms.gle/Df8Zp3HxjzbrFcEn7>) available online for reporting of any violations of the EDI policy. This can be used by any individual or a project participant to communicate issues relating to EDI related violations by individuals while representing OCEAN:ICE (to be received by the EDI contact, i.e. Women in Polar Science, WiPS). The complainant can make anonymous reports, and these will be

investigated internally by the Scientific Steering Committee (and GA if needed). However any information provided will help OCEAN:ICE to understand the prevalence of such incidents / behaviour, and corrective actions could be put in place.

If the complainant has reported violations of this EDI policy with full contact details, and with a request to take the complaint further, the EDI contact will bring this up at the next Scientific Steering Committee meeting where each case will be considered on its own merit. The Scientific Steering Committee must not make assumptions that complaints are a result of 'over-sensitivity' and must take them seriously and deal with them sympathetically and with integrity. The Scientific Steering Committee may refer the issue to the General Assembly if considered necessary for a decision, and further action. Further action may include taking the report on to the relevant employing organisation (/employer), and the OCEAN:ICE funding agencies.

Evaluation

Understanding that this EDI policy is in place to make everyone feel welcome and accepted, especially those that are socially excluded, marginalised or under-represented. It is about encouraging participation so that everyone feels valued, respected and involved thereby fostering a sense of belonging. As a project we acknowledge that this is a very fast changing field, and hence we have a built in review process to ensure that we can address any changes and concerns raised. Further evaluation of the policy will be carried out by presenting it at relevant academic conferences, where feedback will be collected from experts in the field.

Direct feedback from project participants

This policy will be open to continuous improvement based on feedback from the participants, and will be updated throughout the project. Breakout sessions will be conducted at the project General Assemblies to collect feedback from participants, including considerations for further improvements to this policy, and ensure this is reflected in the EDI policy updates.

Links to OCEAN:ICE beneficiary organisations' EDI, and any other relevant policies

- APECS: [DEI Resources](#)
- University of Bristol: [EDI Policy Statement | Equity, Diversity and Inclusion Team | University of Bristol](#)
- UKRI-BAS:

[UKRI's equality, diversity and inclusion strategy](#)

[NERC diversity and inclusion living action plan 2022 to 2025 – UKRI](#)

[Gender equality plan 2022 to 2026 – UKRI](#)

- Danish Meteorological Institute : [DMI's ligestillingsplan vedr. Horizon Europe ansøgninger](#)
- University of Gothenburg: [Policy, rules and plans: Equal opportunities, gender equality and equal treatment – Staff Portal - University of Gothenburg](#)

Glossary of EDI terminology

[A-Z Index | European Institute for Gender Equality](#)

Form for reporting violations of EDI policy in OCEAN:ICE

The project has made an anonymous form (<https://forms.gle/Df8Zp3HxjzbrFcEn7>) available online, on the OCEAN:ICE website for reporting of any violations of the EDI policy.

Revision and updates of EDI policy in OCEAN:ICE

A first revision of the EDI policy was planned in February 2024 by the same drafting team involved in its original editing. Follow up revisions will be added on a yearly basis or within the reporting periods. This deliverable will not be updated, but the revised EDI policy will be published on the project website: <https://ocean-ice.eu/about/oceanice-equality-diversity-and-inclusion-policy-edi/>

Impact

This deliverable is transversal to all objectives (as listed in the description of the action) expected to be achieved by this project. By fostering an inclusive and diverse workspace for the project, the project benefits from a broader range of talents and perspectives, which enhances the research and drives greater innovation. An EDI policy helps ensure that the teams can work smoothly within and across all Work Packages and that an adequate integration of the EDI policy is implemented across all teams. Thus this deliverable indirectly contributes to the achievement of all the objectives of the project itself as described in the description of the action below.

WiPS representatives have been invited to provide keynote lectures, or opening remarks at many Antarctic and Arctic conferences (like the SOOS Symposium, Arctic Science Summit Week), and they have used the OCEAN:ICE EDI policy as an example in their speech. The deliverable we have created here will be shared further via the EU Polar Cluster and its member projects, ensuring a wider impact. Very few projects in the EU Polar Cluster have such a policy in place, and we will disseminate both the policy itself, as well as the process leading up to it, as best practice. Further, we will ensure that the support of expert organisations like WiPS to create EDI policies is available to projects that have recently started, as funding allows. We will also suggest the inclusion of such deliverables in future projects by utilising the expertise of organisations like WiPS, by including them in upcoming proposals. This way, a topical EDI deliverable can be tailor-made and customised appropriately for the project or proposal at hand.

We will ensure the suggestion of inclusion of an EDI policy, and knowledge of organisations like WiPS that work in the EDI space, is provided to upcoming proposals, sent to project teams or proposal support teams within member organisations of OCEAN:ICE. Both the developed EDI policy, and the experience of developing it are invaluable for organisations and project proposals being put together and will help broaden the impact of this deliverable.